

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL POLICY

Inomjon Khabibullaev

Dilnovoz Azimova

Umida Sherko`ziyeva

Students of Gulistan State University, Faculty of Digital Economy and Innovation.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11318954>

Annotation of the article. *The article is aimed at the scientific justification of economic reforms in the formation and development of market relations in the conditions of modern regional economic policy and multi-system economy.*

Key words: *regional policy, single economic space, depression, specialization, small industrial zones, localization, industrialization.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ

Аннотация к статье. *Целью статьи является научное обоснование экономических реформ в условиях становления и развития рыночных отношений в условиях современной региональной экономической политики и многосистемной экономики.*

Ключевые слова: *региональная политика, единое экономическое пространство, депрессия, специализация, малые промышленные зоны, локализация, индустриализация.*

Introduction. At the same time, an in-depth analysis of the development path of our country, today's world market situation has changed dramatically, and the competition is becoming stronger in the conditions of globalization. and requires implementation.

In particular, to strengthen macroeconomic stability and maintain high economic growth rates, to increase the competitiveness of the national economy, to modernize and rapidly develop agriculture, to continue institutional and structural reforms to reduce state participation in the economy, to protect the right to private property. and to further strengthen its priority position, to stimulate the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, to comprehensively and proportionately develop the socio-economic development of regions, districts and cities, to actively attract foreign investments to the sectors and regions of our country's economy by improving the investment environment as a priority task is set.

Analysis and results. In the conditions of globalization and multilateral economy, the role of regional aspects of the development of economic systems is growing at the macro-economic and mega level, arising from the socio-economic balance in regional development. On

the one hand, globalization is a process that unites the actions of different countries (capital, labor, natural, etc.) for the efficient use of resources and maximum satisfaction of society's needs, which means the indiscriminate movement of resources that leads to international exploitation.

In addition, the mega-corporations that ensure the maximum use of these resources greatly influence the scale of corporations. Hyper-urbanization, centralized trends, environmental problems, depressed production and unemployment growth in the regions of many countries require a science-based approach to managing regional development.

Modern regional economic policy should take into account the location of industrial enterprises, first of all, taking into account the sustainable advantages of a certain area (territorial costs, labor, population concentration, availability of infrastructure, service and distribution areas, etc.).

It creates the need to minimize production costs, taking into account microeconomic factors, in order to maximize profits.

At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the interaction of industries and foreign trade with all necessary resources. Each economic region must be a single market within its borders due to interregional competition. It is necessary to take into account not individual isolated industrial enterprises, but interconnected enterprises. This theoretical direction is also characterized by the minimization of costs (not only transport, but also production) in order to maximize revenues, taking into account constant prices, rent, supply and demand functions and elements of dynamics. There is a need to create a general theory of placement based on models of regional economic balance.

Regional policy in Uzbekistan is primarily aimed at regulating the socio-economic development of regions and reducing regional differences. The means of implementing this policy include: the existing system of financing local budgets, state-targeted social programs, state investment policy, directed to underdeveloped regions with excess labor resources, as well as creation of new transport communications, regional socio-economic development programs. Ko'p ukladli iqtisodiyot sharoitida bozor munosabatlarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda iqtisodiy islohotlarni ilmiy asoslash zarur.

Regional economy is of special importance for the scientific justification of radical economic reforms. The need to develop the national economy in the conditions of market relations creates inequalities between economic regions.

In regionally depressed economic areas, unemployment increases, production declines, hyper-urbanization of the population, and serious environmental problems.

Therefore, in the conditions of market relations, it is necessary to organize production taking into account economic and social factors.

The organization of production and socio-economic development of economic regions requires the development of strategic positions, contributing to the improvement of the compatibility of production forces with production relations, the territorial structure of the economy and the territorial organization of the economy in the republic as a whole. The development of production and economy in economic regions mainly depends on the economic policy of the state. In turn, the regional policy of the state is interconnected with the policy of economic regions.

The regional policy of the republic is an integral part of the national strategy of socio-economic development and covers the following main areas:

- determination of territorial aspects of economic development and regional economic level;
- development of new areas, resources and production;
- ensuring the solution of national economic issues;
- improving the regional policy regionally, taking into account the demographic and agrarian policy of the state;

The main task of regional policy should be derived from the country's regional policy. This policy should include the following elements:

- development of underdeveloped regions of the economic zone and modernization of production;
formation of new industries operating on the basis of local raw materials;
- provision of necessary socio-economic conditions for the development of the economic region;

With such an approach, only the organization of the economic zone can achieve the planned development of the economy.

In our republic, national and regional politics are conducted regularly, and of course it is very important.

There is a large territory of Uzbekistan, and economic regions differ in terms of natural-geographical, socio-demographic, economic nature, and this requires a separate approach to each economic region.

To solve these problems, it is necessary to do the following:

1. Taking into account the specific characteristics of each economic region in the economic reform of the network structures of production.
2. Optimizing interregional economic relations, optimizing existing balances, especially by restoring economic agrarian regions.
3. Alleviation of social conflicts between urban and rural life.
4. Finding and developing production in the law of supply and demand for more complete development of natural and labor resources.
5. Scientifically rational and rational placement of new industrial projects, taking into account the local natural resources of the economic regions.

In modern conditions, the importance of regional politics is increasing. The reasons for this are:

- the need to take into account not only internal but also external factors when implementing economic reforms based on the specific characteristics of economic regions;
- independence and disproportionality of reform of production and economic systems, fragmentation of economic regions both in economic regions and on the scale of the whole country;
- the dependence of the economic regions on the supply of food, raw materials, industrial and technical purposes, that is, the existing limited possibilities of self-sufficiency and self-management are the main task of regional policy in the economic regions of the Republic There should be a wide development of urban life in all social and socio-economic conditions in cities and in all types of rural settlements.

Thus, in regional policy, attention should be shifted to the construction and development of new regions, stabilization of the depressed state of old regions and their elimination. This leads to the improvement of the socio-economic situation.

In the implementation of regional policy, the development of regions (interregional stratification) is shifted to the concept of polarized development policy based on stimulation of "points" and "poles" of economic growth. The main tools of this policy include the creation of free industrial economic zones (EIZ), free economic zones (EIZ), small industrial zones (KSZ), implementation of large investment projects, and others.

In almost all countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, free economic zones are used as an effective tool of regional policy. In our country, the development of production based on new and high technologies, the expansion of exports and the attraction of local and foreign investments to create favorable conditions for economic development are the strategic goals and

tasks of free economic zones in our country. Free economic zones are an element of the republic's scientific-innovative and investment policy, they can test new mechanisms of economic management, opportunities to attract investments to the development of priority industries and sectors that determine innovative, resource-saving, socially oriented features.

In recent years, a distinctive feature of Uzbekistan's regional policy implementation is the concept of adapting regional differentiation to the "specialized development" model. Automobile plants in the cities of Asaka and Samarkand, Shortan gas-chemical complex, Bukhara oil refinery, Navoi, Angren, Jizzakh

Summary. The regional policy of the state is a framework of activities for managing the political, economic, social and ecological development of the country on a large scale, regionally, reflecting the mutual relations between the state, regions and regions. Regional policy is a system of legislative, administrative and environmental measures that help to more rationally distribute productive forces, eliminate differences in the development of individual regions. That is, in the end, the main goal is to ensure balance in regional development and eliminate regional disparity. This goal requires maintaining a certain balance in regional politics: centralization and decentralization, statehood and autonomy, natural differences and regulation.

Modern regional economic policy should take into account the location of industrial enterprises, first of all, taking into account the sustainable advantages of a certain area (territorial costs, labor, population concentration, availability of infrastructure, service and distribution areas, etc.).

REFERENCES

1. Burxanov A.X. va boshqalar. Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot. Darslik. Ziyο nashr-matba. Guliston 2021. 538 bet.
2. Burxanov A., Raxmatov K. Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot. O`quv qo`llanma. Ziyο nashr-matba. Guliston 2020. 428 bet.
3. www.grandars.ru Особенности региональной политики.
4. www.biznes-daily.uz Региональная экономическая политика Узбекистана в годы независимости.
5. Burkhanov A. et al. ISSUES STRENGTHENING THE FOOD BASE IN ANIMAL HUSBANDRY—A FACTOR OF INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 53-58.

6. Khadzhimuradovich B. A. FORMATION OF NEW ECONOMIC RELATIONS IS THE KEY TO STABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE //" Conference on Universal Science Research 2023". – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 4. – С. 9-15.